

Bra000758 is a part of a R-gene pair

Bra000758

Predicted Domain Structure

Predicted Gene Structure

IGV view of Mapped RNA-Seq data

1 kbp

Bra003867

Predicted Domain Structure

Predicted Gene Structure

IGV view of Mapped RNA-Seq data

1 kbp